

#	Query	Results
S70	S21 AND S61 AND S69	1,344
S69	S62 OR S63 OR S64 OR S65 OR S66 OR S67 OR S68	159,345
S68	(MH "Length of Stay") OR (Length* N3 stay*)	65,036
S67	(transition* N3 home*)	1,719
S66	(post N3 discharg*) OR post-discharg*	4,872
S65	(MH "Patient Discharge+") OR "discharg*"	101,476
S64	(hospital* N3 home*)	8,971
S63	(return* N3 home*)	2,046
S62	(short N3 time N3 stay*) OR (short N3 term N3 stay*) OR (short N3 time N3 hospitalization*) OR (short N3 term N3 hospitalization*)	359
S61	S22 OR S23 OR S24 OR S25 OR S26 OR S27 OR S28 OR S29 OR S30 OR S31 OR S32 OR S33 OR S34 OR S35 OR S36 OR S37 OR S38 OR S39 OR S40 OR S41 OR S42 OR S43 OR S44 OR S45 OR S46 OR S47 OR S48 OR S49 OR S50 OR S51 OR S52 OR S53 OR S54 OR S55 OR S56 OR S57 OR S58 OR S59 OR S60	1,383,300
S60	(MH "Adaptation, Physiological+") OR (MH "Adaptation, Psychological+") OR (emotional N3 adjust*) OR (adapt* N3 behav*) OR (psychologic* N3 adjust*) OR (adapt* N3 psychologic*) OR (physiologic* N3 adjust*) OR (physiologic* N3 adapt*)	49,976
S59	(MH "Prehabilitation") OR "Prehabilitation*" OR (preoperative N3 exercise*) OR (pre-operative exercise*) OR (preoperative N3 educat*) OR (pre-operative N3 educat*)	2,708
S58	(MH "Text Messaging+") OR (text N3 messag*)	5,450
S57	(mobile N3 team\$)	368

S56	(MH "Rehabilitation+") OR "rehab*" OR "convalescence*"	414,089
S55	(MH "Recovery+") OR "recover*"	132,487
S54	(MH "Home Rehabilitation+") OR (home N3 rehab*)	3,964
S53	(MH "Self-Management") OR (self N3 manag*) OR "self-manag*"	20,842
S52	(MH "Multidisciplinary Care Team+") OR (multidisciplin* N3 car*) OR (multi-disciplin* N3 car*)	52,501
S51	(MH "Health Promotion+") OR (health N3 promot*)	101,968
S50	(MH "Self Care+") OR (self N3 car*) OR (self-car*)	79,036
S49	(MH "Continuity of Patient Care+") OR (patient N3 car*) OR (car* N3 behav*)	376,316
S48	(MH "Patient Education+") OR (patient* N3 educat*) OR (MH "Patient Discharge Education") OR (client* N3 educat*)	103,098
S47	(clinic* N3 teach* N3 method*)	3,386
S46	(MH "Analgesia+") OR "analgesia*"	32,889
S45	(MH "Pain Management") OR (pain N3 manag*)	36,008
S44	(instruction* N3 film*) OR (instruction* N3 video*)	812
S43	(MH "Simulations+") OR "simulation*"	64,472
S42	(active N3 post-discharg* N3 surveillanc*)	3
S41	(remote N3 monitor*)	2,891
S40	(followup N3 support*) OR (follow-up N3 support*)	2,173
S39	(followup N3 car*) OR (follow-up N3 car*)	1,765
S38	(MH "After Care") OR (after N3 car*) OR "after-car*"	59,636

S37	(real-time N3 support*)	329
S36	(MH "Home Visits") OR (home N3 visit*) OR (house N3 call*)	12,379
S35	((electronic N3 health N3 service*) OR "ehealth" OR e-health) N5 ((MH "Communication+") OR "communicat*")	4,059
S34	(MH "Nursing Informatics") OR (nurs* N3 inform*) OR (health N3 inform* N3 techn*)	19,372
S33	(inform* N3 application*)	2,106
S32	(MH "Medical Informatics") OR (inform* N3 communicat* N3 techn*)	7,670
S31	(health N3 communica*) OR (medic* N3 inform*)	33,199
S30	(MH "Videoconferencing+") OR (video N3 conf*) OR "video- conf*"	5,247
S29	(MH "Telenursing") OR "telenurs*"	2,288
S28	(MH "Telerehabilitation") OR (tele N3 rehab*) OR "tele-rehab*"	456
S27	(MH "Mobile Applications") OR (mobile N3 application*)	11,588
S26	(MH "Tablets") OR "tablet*"	12,167
S25	(MH "Smartphone") OR "smartphone*" OR "smart-phone*"	10,563
S24	(MH "Telephone+") OR "telephone*" OR (MH "Cellular Phone+") OR (cell N3 phone*) OR (mobile N3 phone*)	56,519
S23	(MH "Telehealth+") OR "telehealth*" OR "tele-health*"	31,751
S22	(MH "Telemedicine+") OR "telemedicine*"	25,859
S21	S6 OR S19 OR S20	56,847
S20	(spine* OR spinal* OR lumbar*) N7 (surg* OR neurosurg* OR orthop#ed*)	46,852

S19	S12 AND S18	33,549
S18	S13 OR S14 OR S15 OR S16 OR S17	121,086
S17	(MH "Lumbar Vertebrae") OR (lumbar N3 vertebra*)	20,019
S16	(MH "Spine+") OR "spine" OR (spin* N3 column*)	70,151
S15	(MH "Spinal Diseases+") OR (spinal N3 disease*)	40,175
S14	(MH "Radiculopathy") OR "radicul*"	5,323
S13	(MH "Low Back Pain") OR (low N3 back N3 pain) OR (back N3 pain)	42,440
S12	S7 OR S8 OR S9 OR S10 OR S11	201,239
S11	(spin* N3 surg*)	21,739
S10	(MH "Orthopedic Surgery+")	125,768
S9	(MH "Orthopedics") OR "orthop#edic*"	75,872
S8	(neurosurgical N3 procedure*)	558
S7	(MH "Neurosurgery+") OR "neurosurgery"	33,563
S6	S1 OR S2 OR S3 OR S4 OR S5	27,879
S5	(MH "Spinal Diseases+/SU")	13,410
S4	(MH "Spinal Fusion") OR (spin* N3 fusion*)	12,248
S3	(MH "Decompression, Surgical+") OR (surg* N3 decompression*)	7,147
S2	(MH "Diskectomy") OR "diskectom*" OR "discectom*"	3,768
S1	(MH "Laminectomy") OR "laminectomy*"	3,136